

DETERMINANTS OF ADOPTION OF FARO-44 RICE ON THE LIVELIHOOD OF RICE FARMERS' IN SABON-GARI LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the determinants of adoption of faro-44 rice on the livelihood of rice farmers' in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. The study area was purposively selected due to its prominence in rice production and their subsequent adoption of the improved variety. Multistage sampling technique was used to select one hundred and six (106) rice farmers from four villages across two major wards with high rice production intensity. The theoretical frame-work upon which the work was hinged is the theory of adoption of innovation. Data was collected using structured questionnaire and was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics, including logistic regression, Pearson correlation, and paired t-tests. Results revealed that the mean age of respondents was between 41–50 years, with 98.1% being male and 90.7% married. The mean farm size was 2.78 hectares, and 48.6% of the respondents had tertiary education. Logistic regression showed the following as the major determinants of adoption: Education, access to credit, marital status, and off-farm occupation were statistically significant factors influencing adoption. Education was found to have a strong and positive influence, with a coefficient of 0.107 and a p-value of 0.000. Access to credit also had a significant positive effect (coefficient = 0.032, p = 0.001), Marital status showed a statistically significant negative relationship with adoption (p = 0.012), possibly due to household responsibilities or financial burden limiting the capacity of married farmers to take risks associated with new technologies. Off-farm occupation had a large negative coefficient (-0.940) and was also highly significant (p = 0.000), this implies that the more the respondents engage in off-farm activities the less the time, energy and resources for agricultural activities which entails adoption of Faro-44 and that it is highly significant means that off-farm activities is very strategic to adoption as it can greatly affect adoption of faro-Faro-44 negatively and positively.

Key Words: FARO-44, Pearson correlation, logistic regression, adoption, farmers, livelihood

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

Rice is a type of grain derived from the seed of *Oryza sativa* (Asian rice) or *Oryza glaberrima* (African rice), two species within the grass family, Poaceae (Smith, 2020). It is one of the most widely consumed staple foods globally, especially across Asia, Africa, and Latin America, where it forms a dietary cornerstone (Jones & Lee, 2019). Rice is primarily valued as a source of carbohydrates, which supply energy, and it is low in both fat and sodium, making it an essential component of the diet for billions of people (Chen et al., 2018). Rice is believed to have originated in the Yangtze River Valley of China over 9,000 years ago, where archaeological findings indicate early domestication of wild rice (*Oryza sativa*), which later spread throughout Asia (Fuller, Sato, Castillo, Qin, Weiss-Kopf and Kingloea-Banham, 2010).

The global land area cultivated for rice is approximately 162 million hectares, with Asia accounting for around 90% of this area (Food and Agriculture Organization [FAO], 2021). Major rice-producing countries, including China, India, Indonesia, Bangladesh, and Vietnam, contribute significantly to this figure, as these countries collectively account for a large portion of rice cultivation worldwide. Outside Asia, other regions with substantial rice cultivation include parts of Africa, Latin America, and the southern United States. This vast cultivation area reflects rice's role as a staple food for over half the world's population, especially in Asia and Africa, where rice is a primary source of nutrition and food security (FAO, 2021).

The total output of rice in West Africa is estimated to be around 11 million metric tons annually (Africa Rice Center, 2021). The total output of rice in Africa is estimated to be around 14 million metric tons annually (United States Department of Agriculture [USDA], 2022). Nigeria, is the largest producer, with an annual output of approximately 5 million metric tons. Mali, the second-largest producer, producing around 1.5million metric tons annually. Senegal, the third-largest, with an output of about 1.2million metric tons each year. Côte d'Ivoire, the fourth-largest producer, contributing approximately 1 million metric tons annually (Africa Rice Center, 2022).

FARO-44 was developed by the National Cereals Research Institute (NCRI) in Nigeria, in collaboration with the Africa Rice Center. This development was part of efforts to improve rice production in Nigeria by introducing high-yielding, resilient varieties suited to local conditions (NCRI, 1990).

The introduction and adoption of improved rice varieties, such as FARO-44, has been heralded as a significant advancement in agricultural practices aimed at enhancing rice productivity and food security in Nigeria. However, in the context of Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, the actual impact of FARO-44 adoption on the livelihoods of rice farmers remains inadequately unclear as most of the futures are still battling with low output and low income. Despite the availability of this high-yielding variety, many farmers continue to face challenges related to production, such as limited access to quality seeds, inadequate agricultural extension services, and poor infrastructure. Moreover, the socio-economic effects of adopting FARO-44 such as changes in income levels, food security, and overall quality of life for farmers have not been sufficiently documented, empirically as there is limited or dearth of documented evidence on the effect of adoption of NCRI recommended FARO-44 variety. There is also a need to investigate whether the expected benefits of increased yields translate into tangible improvements in the livelihoods of rice farmers in the study area.

Consequently, this study seeks to explore the extent to which the adoption of FARO-44 has influenced the agricultural productivity, income generation, and overall well-being of rice farmers in Sabon Gari, identifying both the advantages and the constraints to effective adoption. This understanding is crucial for developing targeted interventions and policies as well as development of other technology that can support rice farmers in maximizing the benefits of improved rice varieties. It is worthy of note FARO-44 was rolled out to the public in 1990 and since then it has remained in the public space but as the time these research there is dearth literature as regard it adoption.

1.2 Conceptual Frame-Work

The conceptual framework is based on the adoption of FARO-44 among members and non-members of tomato farmers. It is made up of independent, and dependent variables. The independent variables are socioeconomic and institutional factors. These variables are expected to influence adoption of FARO-44. The adoption of FARO-44 will serve as the dependent variable. The adoption of FARO-44 is expected to result in increased yield and increased income.

1.3 Economic Theory of Adoption

This theory of adoption as developed by Dirk Bethmann and Micheal Kvasnicka is otherwise known as the theory of maximization of utility and is used to explain the response of farmers towards a newly introduced technology (Adesina and Seid 1995). This theory states that farmer will adopt a given technology if the utility derived from the new technology exceeds that of the previous (old) one. This theory is also based on the assumption that a farmer or potential adopter makes choice or selection with respect to the satisfaction that may be derived from the technology. He could also make choice on the maximization of the expected utility subject to prices, policies, personal characteristics and natural resources as well as the cost-benefit and resource constraints. The theory over rely on utility maximization and cost-benefit analysis, failing for crucial social Psychological and contextual factors that influence adoption decisions and also the nature of the adoption adoption process over time

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study area

Sabon Gari Local Government Area (LGA) is located in the northern part of Kaduna State, Nigeria. It has 23 LGAs in the state and is recognized for its diverse population and economic activities, their primarily economic activity is agriculture (NBS, 2020). Sabon Gari covers an area of approximately 470 square kilometers and is bordered by Zaria LGA to the north and Giwa LGA to the west, making it a strategic location for agricultural trade and development (NBS, 2020).

3.2 Sampling procedure and Sample Size

Multi stage sampling technique was adopted for this study, In the first stage, a purposive sampling procedure was used to select two wards with high concentration of rice farmers from the study area, in the second stage, from the two wards, two villages is selected due to the high volume of rice production making total of four villages, in the third stage, Taro Yamane formula

is used to proportionately select a sample size of 106 rice farmers from a sample frame of 145 farmers, gotten from a list of registered farmers obtained from the Kaduna State Agricultural development program.

TARO YAMANE formula was used to obtain the sample size

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

$$n_i = \frac{n * N_i}{N}$$

Where;

n =sample size

N =Total population

e = level of significant 0.05

Proportionate sampling technique will be used to determine the number of respondent in each of the selected village

Where,

N=Number of villages,

x=Number of farmers per village,

X= Total number of farmers,

n=Sample size for the study.

Table 3.1: Sampling Frame and Sampling Size

LGAs	Wards	Villages	Sample frame	Sample size
Sabon gari	Samaru	Bomo	44	32
		Ungwan Naibi	25	18
	Dogarawa	Sakadadi	39	29
		Ungwan	37	28
	Salihu	Total	145	106

Source: field survey, 2025.

3.3 Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics such as tables, means, percentages and charts was used.

3.4 Inferential statistics

Inferential statistics such as Logit regression model and t-test was used to determine the socio-economic factor that influence adoption in the study area, and also to determine the effect of adoption of FARO-44 on the adopters in the study area.

t-test was also used to determine the effect of adoption of FARO-44 in the study area. The expression of t-test formula

$$t = \frac{\bar{X} - \bar{Y}}{\sqrt{\sum \frac{X}{nx} - \bar{X} + \sum \frac{Y}{ny} - \bar{Y}}}$$

\bar{X} = non adopters of FARO-44, \bar{Y} = adopters of FARO-44, X = Data for the first group (Group X), Y = Data for the second group (Group Y), nx = Sample size of the Group/population, ny = Sample size of the Group /population.

Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC), Pearson product moment correlation coefficient will be used to test the hypothesis Ho: There is no significant relationship between some selected socio-economic characteristics and adoption of improved FARO-44's. The expression of PPMC.

$$r_{xr} = \frac{n \sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where:

r = correlation coefficient, x = independent variable, y = dependent variable, n = total number of observations, \sum = summation

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

As evident in table 1, 98.1% of the respondents were male, while 1.9% were female. This indicates that rice farming in the study area is male-dominated. This aligns with findings from Ojo and Ogunyemi (2019), who observed that male dominance in rice production is common in Northern Nigeria due to cultural and labor-intensive factors that favour male participation, majority of respondents were between 41–50 years (30.8%), followed by 31–40 years (25.2%) and 61–70 years (16.8%). The average age group was 3.20, which reflects an active farming population. According to Ibrahim, Abdullahi and Umar (2020) farmers within this age bracket are usually more energetic and productive, capable of making rational decisions regarding technology adoption also most respondents were married (90.7%), with a few being widowed (4.7%), divorced (2.8%), or single (1.9%). This is consistent with the study of Yahaya and Garba (2018), which found that marital responsibilities often motivate farmers to increase productivity through innovation adoption. In the same vein Table 1 illustrates that significant number of respondents (48.6%) had tertiary education, followed by (27.1%) with secondary education, Quranic (16.8%), and non-formal education (7.5%). The finding is consistent with that of Adewuyi & Akinola, (2019) who reported that higher educational levels enhance understanding and willingness to adopt new farming technologies, the house hold size of 6–10 members was (44.9%), followed by 11–15 members (29.0%), 1–5 members (19.6%), and 16–20 members (6.5%). Large household sizes can provide the necessary labour for farming activities, facilitating adoption of improved practices (Nwachukwu Onyemachi and Okonkwo

(2021). About 36.4% of the respondents were farming on 0.5–1.5 hectares and others on larger plots. The mean farm size was 2.78 hectares. Farm size often influences input usage and adoption behavior, with medium-to-large farms more likely to adopt improved rice varieties (Omotayo, Yusuf and Adewale 2020).

Table1: distribution of Socioeconomic characteristics of rice farmers

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage%	
Gender	Male	105	98.1%	
	Female	2	1.9%	
Age	20–30	9	8.4%	
	31–40	27	25.2%	
	41–50	33	30.8%	
	51–60	15	14.0%	
	61–70	18	16.8%	
	71–80	5	4.7%	
	Mean Age Group			3.20
Marital Status	Single	2	1.9%	
	Married	97	90.7%	
	Divorced	3	2.8%	
	Widowed	5	4.7%	
Education Level	Non-formal	8	7.5%	
	Secondary (combined)	29	27.1%	
	Tertiary	52	48.6%	
	Quranic	18	16.8%	
Household Size	1–5 members	21	19.6%	
	6–10 members	48	44.9%	
	11–15 members	31	29.0%	
	16–20 members	7	6.5%	
	Mean Household Size			2.22
Farming Experience	Less than 5 years	3	2.8%	
	5–10 years	23	21.5%	
	11–15 years	19	17.8%	
	Above 15 years	62	57.9%	
	Mean Farming Experience			3.31
Farm Size (Ha)	0.5–1.5	39	36.4%	
	1.6–2.5	14	13.1%	
	2.6–3.5	19	17.8%	
	3.6–4.5	15	14.0%	
	4.6–5.5	9	8.4%	
	5.6–6.5	9	8.4%	
	6.6–7.5	2	1.9%	
	Mean Farm Size			2.78

Source: field survey,2025.

4.2 Socio-economic Factors Influencing Adoption of FARO-44 Rice Variety

Education, access to credit, marital status, and off-farm occupation were statistically significant factors influencing adoption. Education was found to have a strong and positive influence, with a coefficient of 0.107 and a p-value of 0.000, suggesting that farmers with higher educational attainment were significantly more likely to adopt FARO-44. This supports the findings of Odoemenem and Obinne (2019), who reported that educated farmers tend to be more receptive to agricultural innovations due to better access to and understanding of technical information. Access to credit also had a significant positive effect (coefficient = 0.032, $p = 0.001$), indicating that farmers who could obtain credit were more likely to adopt the variety. Credit availability eases financial constraints, allowing farmers to invest in improved seeds and complementary inputs. This aligns with the study by Omonona (2018), which identified credit as a key enabler of agricultural technology uptake in Nigeria. Marital status showed a statistically significant negative relationship with adoption ($p = 0.012$), possibly due to household responsibilities or financial burden limiting the capacity of married farmers to take risks associated with new technologies. Although the coefficient is relatively small, the significance implies that marital dynamics may influence decision-making in agricultural households. Off-farm occupation had a large negative coefficient (-0.940) and was also highly significant ($p = 0.000$), suggesting that farmers with income-generating activities outside agriculture were less likely to adopt FARO-44. This could be due to time constraints or competing investment priorities. Nwalieji and Ajayi (2023) noted that part-time farmers often show lower adoption rates for new technologies, especially when farming is not their primary livelihood. Other variables such as age ($p = 0.054$) approached significance, with a negative coefficient suggesting that younger farmers were more inclined to adopt the variety.

However, household size, farm size, cooperative membership, and farming experience did not show statistically significant effects, even though they may still play supportive roles in adoption behavior. Overall, the findings underscore that educational level and financial access are the most consistent drivers of adoption, while socio-demographic factors such as marital status and occupation introduce nuanced variations in adoption patterns.

Table2: Distribution of Respondents Based on socio-economic Factors Influencing Adoption of FARO-44 Rice Variety

Variable	Dy/Dx	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z-value	P-value
Age	-0.155	-0.155	0.080	-1.96	0.054
Marital Status	-0.054	-0.054	0.232	-2.45	0.012
Household Size	0.107	0.107	0.188	0.57	0.568
Education	0.107	0.107	0.090	3.49	0.000
Farm Size (Ha)	-0.138	-0.138	0.161	-0.85	0.392
Farming Experience	-0.615	-0.615	0.825	-0.75	0.456
Member of Cooperative	1.499	1.499	1.593	0.94	0.347
Other Occupation (Farming)	-0.940	-0.940	0.104	-9.04	0.000
Access to Credit	0.032	0.032	0.015	4.30	0.001

Source: field survey, 2025.*= Significant at 10% **= Significant at 5% ***= Significant at 1%

4.3 Hypothesis Testing in Relation to H_0

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between some selected socio-economic characteristics and the adoption of improved FARO-44 rice variety.

A Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test between the adoption of FARO-44 and selected socio-economic variables, including gender, age, marital status, household size, education, farm size, farming experience, cooperative membership, occupation, access to credit, and source of credit. Findings revealed that several socio-economic variables — such as age ($r = -0.491$, $p = 0.000$), education ($r = 0.362$, $p = 0.000$), farm size ($r = 0.712$, $p = 0.000$), years of experience ($r = -0.241$, $p = 0.013$), membership of cooperative ($r = 0.830$, $p = 0.000$), access to credit facilities ($r = 0.906$, $p = 0.000$), and source of credit ($r = 0.229$, $p = 0.018$) — had statistically significant relationships with adoption of FARO-44. Therefore, since multiple socio-economic factors showed significant correlations, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion: There is a significant relationship between some selected (age, education, farm size, years of experience, membership of cooperative, access to credit facility and source of credit facility) socio-economic characteristics and the adoption of improved FARO-44 rice variety among farmers in the study area.

Table 3: Summary of Hypothesis Test on Socio-Economic Characteristics and Adoption of FARO-44

Socio-Economic Variable	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value	H_0
Age	-0.491	0.000	Reject
Education	0.362	0.000	Reject
Farm Size	0.712	0.000	Reject
Years of Experience	-0.241	0.013	Reject
Membership of Cooperative	0.830	0.000	Reject
Access to Credit Facility	0.906	0.000	Reject
Source of Credit	0.229	0.018	Reject

Source: field survey, 2025. * = Significant at 10% ** = Significant at 5% *** = Significant at 1%

Conclusion and recommendation

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that FARO-44 has a positive and significant effect on the livelihood of rice farmers in Sabon Gari LGA. The variety has contributed to increased productivity, income, and overall welfare of adopters compared to non-adopters. Socio-economic factors such as education, household size, farming experience, and access to credit were found to significantly influence adoption. It was recommended that: The government and private organizations should improve the reach and capacity of agricultural extension agents to ensure timely and adequate dissemination of information on FARO-44 and other improved technologies and government in collaboration with private individuals should

subsidize and/or facilitate access to improved seeds, fertilizers, and agrochemicals will encourage further adoption and increase productivity.

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